

Advances in plasmonic-based MOF composites, their bio-applications and perspectives in this field

Introduction: Nanomaterials have been used for bio-applications since the late 20st century. In an attempt to tailor and optimize their properties, and by extension their efficiency, composites have attracted considerable attention. In this regard, recent studies on plasmonic nanoparticles and metal-organic framework (NP@MOF) composites suggested these materials show great promise in this field.

Areas covered: This review focused on the more recent scientific advances in the synthetic strategies to optimize plasmonic MOF nanocomposites currently available, as well as their bio-application, particularly as biosensors and therapy.

Expert opinion: Plasmonic MOF nanocomposites have shown great potential as they combine the properties of both materials with proven efficiency in bio-application. On the one hand, nanoMOFs have proven their potential particularly as drug nanocarriers, owing to their exceptional porosity and tunability. On the other hand, plasmonic nanoparticles have been an asset for imaging and phototherapy. Different strategies have been reported to develop these nanocomposites, mainly including core-shell, encapsulation, and in situ reduction. In addition, advanced composite structures should be considered, such as mixed metal nanoparticles, hollow structures or the combination of several approaches. Specifically, plasmonic MOF nanocomposites prove to be attractive stimuli responsive drug delivery systems, phototherapeutic agents as well as highly sensitive biosensors.

1. Introduction

Photo-active nanomaterials have been extensively investigated for applications in biology.[1] Several factors can explain their interest. One of the main reasons being that nanosized materials are favorable to the process of endocytosis, acting as nanocarriers or diagnostic tools, among others.[2] Particularly, plasmonic nanoparticles (NPs) have been the focus of interest due to the property which give its name to this group of material (plasmon). When the NPs are irradiated (with a wavelength superior to the diameter of the particle), the conductive electrons oscillate coherently; which results in the phenomenon defined as Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR), being dependent on its size, shape and composition. Typically, these particles

are chemically based on gold, silver, palladium and platinum. Plasmonic NPs have been reported to have molar absorption extinction coefficient of up to up to $10^{11} \text{ M}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, as well as high scattering cross section, making them more efficient than fluorescent molecules. Furthermore, unlike the latter, plasmonic NPs do not photo-bleach.[3] These properties lead to their use in the field of biomedicine, mainly for bioimaging and immunoassays.

Although plasmonic NPs are highly potent photo-active materials, they present a major drawback: their colloidal stability. NPs in a colloidal solution aggregate and even sinter, leading to a loss of efficiency as LSPR is surface dependent.[4] The most conventional method to avoid the aggregates formation is the surface functionalization of the NPs, by coating or grafting molecules on their surface. Then, the NPs can repel each other either because of charge or steric hindrance.[5,6] Later on, more complex molecules were used as functionalizing agents, to not only stabilize but to give additional properties, such as higher sensitivity.[7,8] As the field of nanomaterials advanced, the research moved to more complex architectures, *i.e.* not only coating NPs with molecules but with materials. As thoroughly mentioned before, LSPR is a surface phenomenon, therefore functionalizing them with porous materials would allow to retain the properties of the NP whilst taking advantage of the porous properties of the added material.

In this context, metal organic frameworks (MOFs) appears to be great candidates since they are highly porous and (chemically and structurally) versatile. They are composed of inorganic units (atoms, clusters, chains, planes or 3 dimensional (3D) structures) linked together by polycomplexant organic linker (Figure 1). They present different topologies which help to understanding the structural properties of the framework. In this sense, secondary building units (SBUs) are critical components of MOFs that can build potentially porous periodic networks by linking multitopic organic ligands. These materials have attracted interest because their exceptional high and ordered porosity ($\sim 10000 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$, [9]) and the possibility to tailor their final properties by selecting the metal ion or linker for desired applications.[10,11] MOFs are reported to have numerous potential applications (gas storage,[12,13] catalysis,[13,14] sensing,[15,16] and drug delivery,[17,18] among others[19,20]). Focusing on bioapplications, the versatility of MOFs implies fine tuning of: i) their biosafety (biocompatible linker and metal), ii) chemical, structural and colloidal stability in the desired media (e.g. solvents, bioentities), iii) association of the active cargo (in the inner outer surface, porosity or as constitutive part of the MOF), modulating pore size and/or functionalizing the pores/surface,[21,22] iv) reducing MOF particle size to the nanoscale,[23] allowing to surpass biological barriers.[17,18]

By combining versatile nanoMOFs and highly photo-efficient plasmonic (NPs), highly potent and selective NP@MOF nanocomposites materials have been synthesized using mainly three different approaches: 1) core-shell, 2) encapsulation and 3) in-situ reduction.[24,25] Such composites have been proposed in various socioeconomically relevant fields (e.g. catalysis, sensors).[26–29] In particular, these materials have shown great promise in biomedicine, including diagnosis and therapy.[30] Thus, this review will first present the state of the art regarding synthetic pathways of NP@MOF nanocomposites, highlighting determining factors for their successful preparation via core-shell, encapsulation and in situ reduction, before focusing on even more advanced structures (e.g. mixed NP,[31,32] in situ galvanic replacement [33,34]) In addition, bio-applications of these nanocomposites will be discussed, presenting examples of biosensors and therapeutic agents.[30]

The aim of this review is to highlight the current state of the art in plasmonic MOF composite in bio-applications, highlighting important factors such as size and stability but also the current

limitations. As well as a perspective on the future of the materials in the field, inspired by the current use in other applications, of more complex plasmonic MOF composite potentially biocompatible.

2. Synthetic approaches

As previously mentioned, MOFs constitute a support by to stabilize NPs, using three main strategies: 1) core-shell, where the NP is first synthesized and the MOF is then grown on its surface,[35,36] 2) wherein the NP and the MOF are separately synthesized and then, mixed in order to allow the NP to penetrate into the MOF porosity,[37,38] and 3) the in-situ reduction or ship-around-bottle,[39,40] metal ions are introduced and reduced inside of the pores of the pre-formed MOF to form NP.[25,41] Lastly, novel approaches will be introduced, such as composites using mixed metal NPs or using more than one of the aforementioned approaches.

2.1 Core-shell composites

The following section will focus on core-shell materials (Figure 2.1). Core-shell refers to a composite with an initial material, the core, on which a second material, the shell, is grown afterwards. The synthesis of a core-shell composite where the core is a NP can be an arduous task, even more so when the shell is a MOF. NP have relatively low stability and depending on their shape they can be eroded away even more.[42–44] Whereas MOFs are highly porous crystalline compounds, generally a considerable portion (easily up to 40%) of the unit cell accounts for void space. Therefore, crystalizing these phases can require very specific conditions which, on one hand, may not be suitable for the NP (degradation/ sintering) and on the other hand, the introduction of the NP in the system changes drastically the thermodynamic and chemical conditions of the system. Thus, the synthesis of core-shell NP@MOF is often the result of a delicate equilibrium. [45]

In order to develop a core-shell nanocomposite, different factors must be considered. The first, an “anchoring point” on the NP surface must be present to allow the MOF growing.[45,46] This concept can be otherwise rephrased as, at least one of the chemical precursors of the MOF (ligand, cation) must have high affinity for the surface of the NP, whether that affinity is due to hydrophobic, electrostatic interactions or hydrogen bonding depends on the nature of the NP surface.[47,48] The second factor arises from a crystallographic base: MOFs and, for example, gold NPs exhibit different crystalline structures.[45] This accounts for a lattice mismatch between the two phases, and tends to reduce the probability of the formation of a nucleus on the surface of the NP.[49,50] Lastly, the synthetic conditions of the MOF must be compatible with the NP colloidal and chemical stability, preventing aggregation, sintering, deformation or degradation. These lasts are particularly relevant when dealing with particles with high surface area to volume ratios (e.g. stars, hollow). [51]

To understand the key point that leads to the formation of a core-shell composite, we will first tackle a widely reported case where the shell is based on zeolitic imidazole frameworks (ZIFs). In particular the microporous (0.34 nm) zinc 2-methylimidazolate ZIF-8 with a secondary building unit (SBU) of truncated octahedron, with zinc coordinated by 4 linkers which is the typical SBU for ZIFs. This MOF has proven to be a suitable candidate for encapsulation of different active ingredients. [52,53] This MOF is the most reported for plasmonic NP@MOF core-shell composite, including examples with different metals, shapes, capping agents and synthesis

conditions, which making it a fortunate case to shed a light on the growth factors on the surface of NPs.

Although other metal NPs have been reported as a core, here we will focus on gold (AuNPs) as it has proven optimal photothermal conversion.[54,55] ZIF-8 has been successfully synthesized using different synthesis routes such as microwave, solvothermal, under reflux; in different solvent (water, methanol); and at different temperatures (from room temperature (RT) to 120°C). The synthetic versatility of this MOF is one of the main reasons for its frequent use: one can select well-established synthesis conditions compatible with the colloidal stability of NPs used as core. However, synthesis conditions are not enough to solve the “anchoring” and crystallographic issues, requiring from capping agents or surface functionalization of the NP. [56,57]

In this matter, Zheng et al.[58] reported the preparation of AuNP@ZIF-8 in aqueous solution using quaternary ammonium surfactants. Such surfactants have shown an important effect on the ZIF-8's crystallization in water, the hydrophobic chain tending to be preferentially anchored on the {100} plane of the MOF. Different gold NPs (nanorods-NRs[59], spheres and nanostars-NSs[60]) were synthesized and the surface functionalized with polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), an amphiphilic polymer. This polymer endowed the NPs with new properties: higher stability in organic solvent (here methanol), and higher biocompatibility (with regards to cetyltrimethylammonium bromide-CTAB, or cetyltrimethylammonium chloride-CTAC). By changing the concentration of the surfactant, they were able to successfully grow ZIF-8 on the AuNPs surface. The obtained nanocomposites exhibited expected LPSR, no change in the AuNPs morphology, and Brunauer, Emmett and Teller (BET) surface area within the expected range for ZIF-8 and with shell thickness of 77.8 ± 11.0 nm. The core-shell structure was confirmed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) tomographic reconstruction. Although ZIF-8 is an interesting MOF, its poor stability in water and biological environments limit should be overcome by the composite coating with e.g. biocompatible polymers. [61,62]

Other ZIF structures have been used in the core-shell approach. The cobalt 2-methylimidazol ZIF-67, isostructural (same SBU) to ZIF-8, presents an attractive feature (fluorescence) although a less biocompatible character than zinc.[63,64] In this matter, multicore-shell AuNS@ZIF-67 of 907 ± 143 nm has been developed. [65] Based on TEM images collected at different reaction times, it is stipulated that the MOF nucleation is heterogeneous and that the AuNSs act as a seed. Thus, MOF nuclei form on defects and curvatures of the seed and then, grow to cover the totality of the NP. The amount of linker also showed an effect on the MOF formation; more linker leading to higher crystallinity and porosity.[49,50] Although the core-shell was not confirmed by 3D reconstruction, the way the MOF crystalizes on the AuNS indicates an actual core-shell composite.

Advances in MOFs led to materials with greater pore size and surface area, as well as photoactive properties, which have recently been applied in the synthesis of plasmonic core-shell @MOF composite.[66,67] In this regard, the MOF NU-901 (NU stands for Northwestern University), based on zirconium oxoclusters and 1,3,6,8-tetrakis-(p-benzoate)-pyrene, where the clusters are 8-connected by the linker to form an scu topology with microporous diamond shaped pores. The MOF was employed for the preparation of nanocomposites as it is highly fluorescent and porous ($S_{\text{BET}} \sim 2000 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$).[68,69] To build the composite, the AuNRs were functionalized with polyethylene glycol (PEG) to increase their stability in organic solvents and PVP for acids.[70] The fast introduction of the linker in the AuNRs colloidal solution led to the formation of NU-1000, being of same composition but different crystalline structure than NU-

901, with 8-connected Zr_6 SBU with mesoporous hexagonal channels and csq topology. Then, controlling the addition rate of the linker by a syringe-pump, the pure monocoreshell AuNR@NU-901 (250±30 nm in length) was successfully prepared,[71,72] as confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy and TEM. The central and homogeneous of the AuNR inferred the core-shell structure. The resulting composite was investigated as a surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) probe to take advantage of sensing properties of the AuNR.[70]

PCN-222 (Porous Coordination Network) is another fluorescent MOF with high surface area. This MOF, based on Zr and a porphyrin ligand (5, 10, 15, 20-tetrakis (4-carboxyphenyl)porphyrin (TCPP)) was selected for its photoactive character. It is important to note that this system can lead to more than one phase, being PCN-222 based on octa-oxocluster the thermodynamically favored phase (2600 m²g⁻¹), and PCN-224 based on hexa-oxoclusters the kinetic one (2000 m²g⁻¹).[73,74] In this regard, Zhou and coworkers studied the effect of trace amounts of water on the synthesis of core-shell nanocomposites with PVP-coated AuNRs. Interestingly, the introduction of water favored the formation of PCN-222 rather than PCN-224.[75] Moreover, it had an effect on the growth of the MOF shell, allowing to control the thickness, the optimized average size at 1%v in diameter and length being 102 ± 15 and 185 ± 30 nm. PCN-222 had strong affinity for the PVP coating: within only four minutes, a thin layer of MOF grew on the NP, TEM images were collected at different reaction time demonstrating the layer by layer growth.[76,77] It can be an indicator that a mono-core shell final composite with a narrow size distribution.

2.2 Encapsulation composites

Another strategy for obtaining NP@MOF nanocomposites is the encapsulation (see Figure 2.2). In the process of encapsulation, the MOF and the NP are synthesized separately and then, put in contact in a colloidal solution.[78,79] The NPs here should penetrate into the pores of the MOF.

From a manipulation standpoint, the standard impregnation process is relatively simple.[80] However, it is important to mention here that the NP dimensions vs. pore size is an important discriminating factor.[81,82] Another parameter to consider is the shape, due to geometric limitations, a rod may fit in one direction but not in the other. As the particles are generally oriented randomly, the odds of such NPs being optimally aligned with the pore is statistically unfavorable, and explains why the reported encapsulation are generally based on spherical NPs, for which the orientation is a non-factor.[83]

The two main methods of encapsulation are impregnation and grinding.[84,85] The latter refers to a mechanical process through which the NPs are forced inside of the pores, generally under dry conditions. Here two issues can arise, the first one comes from the tendency of dried NPs to aggregate, which may be reversible and thus results in a loss or decrease in LSPR intensity. Furthermore, this has a negative effect since they will not fit inside the pores.[86,87] The second concern is related to the MOF. Since they are porous materials with high void volume, when a mechanical stress is applied, they tend to get compressed and a loss of porosity or crystallinity could occur. This explains why grinding is not a commonly used technique.[88]

In contrast, during the process of impregnation, the MOF and NP colloidal solutions are mixed. The main concern related to this strategy is the degradation of one of the materials. This could

arise from the solvents, thus, both materials should be stable under the selected solvent.[89] Additionally, the presence of the NP can lead to a change in the pH, being potentially detrimental to the MOF stability. Adding a high concentrated MOF solution can lessen that effect, at least to an extent. Nevertheless, robust MOFs need to be selected when using this approach. Here, the driving force for the NP to be incorporated inside of the pores is diffusion.[83,86,87] The main factors affecting diffusion are time, temperature and contact surface: high surface area materials favor this process, as well as longer times and higher temperatures.[83,86,87]

Note however here that less examples of encapsulation approach have been reported compared to the others (in situ and core-shell). It may be because synthesizing NPs small enough to pass through pores without a template is a challenging task.[90,91] Nevertheless, some nice examples can be found. For instance, the encapsulation of platinum NPs (PtNPs) in UiO-66 (University of Oslo) in ethanol. This highly biocompatible zirconium MOF, using terephthalic acid as linker, where Zr_6 clusters are 12-connected with bcu topology has a reported surface area of $1200 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$. [92] Zheng et al. described the encapsulation of $2.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$ PtNPs coated with the amphiphatic PVP polymer. The spherical NPs were added drop by drop, to the MOF ($400 \pm 35 \text{ nm}$) solution under vigorous stirring to force the diffusion and kept 12 h to homogenize the dispersion.[93] The composite thermally stable (400°C) and the PtNPs were homogeneously distributed inside of the MOF ; nevertheless, the analysis performed is not sufficient to ascertain the location of the NP (inside of the pores or in the matrix),

Similarly, PtNPs capped with CTAB were introduced in MOF-74(Cu).[94] This copper 5-dihydroxyterephthalate MOF (composed of $\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{CO}_2)_3$ where each copper atom is coordinated to three carboxyl, two hydroxyl groups, and a coordinated ligand, with rod topology. $S_{\text{BET}} \sim 1000 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)[95] was dispersed in a PtNPs water/methanol solution, by sonication followed by stirring refluxate 35°C , leading to a homogeneous distribution of the PtNPs.[94] The size of the PtNP along with the XRD suggest that the NP are in the MOF matrix but not in the pores (large NP, presence of defects). The synergistic effect between Pt and Cu proved to be efficient in the oxygen reduction reaction.

Finally, the groups of Zou and Li reported a composite based on the iron terephthalate MIL-101(Fe) (Materials from Institut Lavoisier), which consists of three oxido vertex-sharing M^{3+} octahedra, which are interconnected by the ligand mtn topology. This MOF is highly biocompatible and porous ($S_{\text{BET}} \sim 3400 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) with T2-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) properties.[96–98] In this case, silver NPs (AgNPs) with 66.66% of the population with a size between 24.5-34.5nm were encapsulated in MIL-101(Fe) using methanol as solvent. Herein, the diffusion was accelerated by using vortex; then the solution was only stirred for 1.5 h.[96] The composite ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$) was analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showing the presence NP inferring that they are on the surface. The composite was used as a sensor for rhodamine 6G, with an enhancement factor of $2.09 \cdot 10^9$ with regard to the AgNPs alone.[99]

2.3 In-situ reduction

The main idea behind the in-situ strategies is the same no matter the reduction route selected.[40,100] The goal here is to form NPs generally inside the pores of the MOF, which means that contrary to the encapsulation the pore opening is not limiting factor. In this strategy, the MOF is firstly synthesized and then, put in contact with the selected metal ion precursor, which is finally reduced to NPs with an oxidation state of 0 through different means of reduction (see Figure 2.3), including chemical, sono- and photo-reduction. There is, however, a problem

that is of concern when pursuing in situ reduction: the degradation of the supporting MOF material, particularly due to overgrowth.[101] If the particles grow beyond the pore size of the MOF, its structure can be destroyed. This explains why the control of the reduction rate and growth of the particle is of utmost importance. However, before the NP grow to a size which destroys the MOF structure, they can create a mechanical strain on the structure. This is translated by the formation of defects. Similarly, when NPs are formed inside of the MOF matrix and not within porosity, structural defects can be noted. Discriminating between NPs in the matrix and in the porosity is a difficult task, generally it is not proven but only inferred. The purpose of the following subsection is to shed a light on the advantages and disadvantages of chemical, sono- and photo- reduction methods.

2.3.1 Chemical reduction

The chemical reduction constitutes the most straightforward route of reduction.[102,103] Using a chemical reducing agent, the metal reduction occurs by standard redox reaction. Indeed, the reductant must be strong enough to reduce the metal but not damaging the MOF structure.[104–106] Moreover, as redox reactions tend to be fast and exothermic, it can be complex to modulate the synthesis to control the growth of the NP and obtain a homogeneous composite.[107,108]

Following this pathway, the in situ chemical reduction of gold in UiO-66-NH₂ and UiO-66 has been investigated. [109] UiO-66- NH₂ is an isostructural analogue of UiO-66 (also same SBU) which differs solely by its linker 2-aminoterephthalic acid and, by extension, the amino group functionalization of the pores. For the nanocomposite (~200nm) synthesis, the MOF was first stirred in a methanol/water solution, then an Au⁺³ aqueous solution was added, and left under stirring in order for the ions to diffuse into the pores. Lastly, NaBH₄ was used as reducing agent and the solution was kept in an ice bath to account for the exothermic reaction that followed and to control the growth of the NPs. The presence of metallic gold was confirmed with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and TEM, but the presented data does not allow to confirm the location of the NP (pores or matrix).[110] Finally, the composite was externally functionalized with anti-furazolidone antibodies, demonstrating to be a powerful tool for the detection of the antibacterial agent furazolidone in food. Immunochromatographic trials showed a significant increase in sensibility when using AuNPs. Besides, gold was reduced using a similar method in the zinc 2-aminoterephthalate IRMOF-3 (Iso Reticular MOF)[111], where nodes and the organic linkers forming a 4 6 cavity.[112] The resulting composite (~200-300nm) showed AuNPs of 3 nm on average (from TEM) and a reduced BET surface area and pore volume (~110 m²·g⁻¹ and 0.41 cm³·g⁻¹ vs. 600 m²·g⁻¹ and 0.44 cm³·g⁻¹ for the empty MOF), estimating a gold loading of 1.6wt% from these values. This composite proved to be an efficient nanocatalyst as well as recyclable in the aerobic oxidation of alcohols and oxidation/imine.

Several examples have been published using similar procedures, supporting the versatility of this method. First with ZIFs, ZIF-7 composed of zinc and benzimidazolone to form SOD SBU, was impregnated with AgNO₃ salt at RT, adding then the NaBH₄ ethanolic solution drop by drop, for thermodynamic reasons.[113] The resulting Au@ZIF-7 nanocomposite (~100nm) showed signs of aggregation and was tested for the catalysis of nitroaromatic compounds and organic dyes, proving not only catalytic activity but also stability over the course of the ten catalytic cycles performed. Another example with a ZIF is the AuNP@ZIF-11 nanocomposite where the AuNP of 7.35 ± 0.95 nm). The MOF composed of zinc and benzimidazole to form rhoh SBU was dispersed

in a gold water-based solution, and placed in an ice bath. [114] The reduction was performed using NaBH₄. The presence of metallic gold was confirmed by XPS and its crystallinity by XRD and high resolution TEM (HRTEM).

In addition, the reduction of Pd and Au was performed in the mesoporous robust chromium terephthalate MIL-101(Cr).[115] In one example, gold was reduced using NaBH₄ at RT to form particles of 1.94 ± 0.16 nm. The resulting AuNP@MIL-101(Cr) was characterized by XRD, XPS proving the presence of AuNPs, the small size of the composite can explain why the material showed some evidence of aggregation.[116] Palladium was reduced in the amino functionalized MIL-101(Cr) analogue using a soft reducing agent (i.e. ethylene glycol in aqueous solution) at 150°C. [21,117] The presence of PdNPs was confirmed by several techniques, including TEM, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and XRD. The resulting composite was used to detect telomerase (see part 3.2), evidencing good reproducibility (10 times with standard deviation of 3% max in the detection essays).

2.3.2 Sono-reduction

Although reports of chemical reduction are more common than sono-chemical ones,[118,119] there are some examples employing the latter technique. Sono-chemical reduction arises from acoustic cavitation. In the case of noble metal reduction, the solvent is paramount. A volatile solvent produces strong radicals through sonolysis; these radicals reducing the metal ions in solution. This route usually leads to smaller particles than with chemical reduction.[120–122] Besides, it has several advantages: the synthesis is very fast and the particles are particularly small and with a narrow size distribution.

In this matter, Pd was reduced inside several UiO-66 derivatives (methoxy, dihydroxy, amino).[123] The reported method explained that sonic agitation in hexane/water was favored to magnetic stirring since the pore diffusion of the metal is favored. Furthermore, the functional groups in the pores make them narrower and therefore harder to access. After homogenization of the MOF(~50nm.) dispersion, the Pd was introduced by sonication, evaluating the effect of the pore functionalization on the NPs d-band center and testing their catalytic activity on the benzoic acid hydrogenation reaction. [123]

2.3.3 Photo-reduction

Finally, the in-situ reduction of the metal can occur through the influence of an electromagnetic radiation, known as photo-reduction.[124,125] This path can be considered as indirect since the metal is not directly reduced by light. Generally, a photo-agent is introduced and, upon irradiation, produces radicals (or other reducing species), which in turn reduce the metal. This approach is highly dependent on the potency of the photo-agent. The size of the particles can be adjusted by mainly changing the irradiation time and the amount of photo-agent. An example of this was developed by Arenas-Vivo et al., reporting the AgNP@MIL-125-NH₂ in situ photo-reduction.[126] MIL-125-NH₂ is a microporous photoactive titanium 2-aminoterephthalate MOF ($S_{\text{BET}} \sim 1900 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), where cyclic octamers of edge- and corner-sharing TiO₅(OH) octahedra are 12-connected to other octahedron by the linker.[127] The very short reaction (15 s) was performed using a very photosensitive photo-initiator (Irgacure 2959) under inert atmosphere in toluene. The resulting composite (~250nm) showed enhanced antibacterial properties with regard to a physical mixture of the two materials. The presence of the AgNP (1.01 ± 0.36 nm) inside of the porosity was confirmed using advanced TEM characterization (tomographic reconstruction).

2.4 Advanced structures

This section will focus on more innovative and complex composite structures: mixed metal NPs, hollow structures, as well as layered and combined approaches composites. Although the obtained materials are more intricate, the fundamentals of the processes employed remain similar. These complex structures arose because of the will to optimize properties. They were developed to tailor the properties toward a desired application (e.g. catalysis, sensing). In reality, it occurs by combining different materials or by finely tuning their localization, shape or size. As such kinds of composite usually imply a complex organization of the materials, or fine localization, they require highly advanced characterization techniques. Indeed, it is not possible to fully characterize complex nanoscale materials without powerful tools.

2.4.1 Mixed nanoparticles nanocomposites

Hereafter, the interest that mixed NPs draws, as well as their synthesis will be explored.[128–130] It is known that bi-metal plasmonic NPs present enhanced LSPR, which cannot be explained by a linear combination of the different metals' dielectric constant and it is a really appealing feature.[131–133]

The group of Wang took advantage of this approach: spherical AuNPs were employed as a support to deposit a layer of palladium (Au/PdNP), which constituted the core on which the MOF-74(Cu) was grown.[134] The resulting Au/PdNP@MOF-74(Cu) composite (707±34nm in length) was used for CO₂ conversion and showed superior catalytic activity for reverse water gas shift reaction compared to single metal NPs. Similarly, Liu et al. have reported core-shell nanocomposites based on mixed metal NPs.[135] In this case, the selected MOF was HKUST-1,[135] a highly porous copper trimesate with tbo topology with a BET surface area of 1400 m²·g⁻¹ and the NPs were AuNP spherical cores with Pt dendrites. The growth of HKUST-1 (Hong Kong University of Science and Technology) was heterogeneous, because both the use of an apolar solvent (benzyl alcohol) and the high concentration tended to favor the formation of numerous nuclei. This heterogeneous nucleation led to an original petal-like morphology, opening up more active sites for catalysis, notably for the liquid-phase hydrogenation of olefin, with up to 25% of conversion. Furthermore, the heterogeneous growth of the MOF is an indicator that the nanocomposite is (~300 nm) is actually core-shell.

Furthermore, the simultaneous in situ reduction of two metals, silver and gold, within the porosity of CTGU-19 (China Three Gorges University) was also explored. This Eu-MOF, composed of 5-(4-carboxyphenyl) picolinic acid, is highly fluorescent. The advantage of using different metal is that it induces photo properties which cannot be obtained with single metal NPs, being of high interest in some applications, particularly for sensors.[136] With this purpose, the MOF was immersed in a solution of the mixed silver and gold salts, and reduced through photo-reduction. Thanks to HRTEM, the presence of crystalline silver and gold was confirmed, by analyzing the interplanar distance and correlating it to the reported ones of silver and gold, confirming the reduction by XPS, but the location was not elucidated. The final nanocomposite was tested for the catalytic study of nitrophenol, a toxic compound used in manufacturing processes (drugs, dye...).[136]

On the other hand, soft chemical reduction, employing dopamine to control the growth of AgNPs, was investigated using the MIL-101(Cr)-SO₃H. [137] The dopamine, a moderate reducing agent, was introduced before the metal ions as it binds to negatively charged sulphonate functional groups of the MOF, and provides a spatial controlled reduction of Ag and Au, leading to a homogeneous distribution of the NPs (~4-8nm) within the MOF.[138] The use of a directed reduction in the pores suggested that the NPs are inside of the pores, but the data presented is not sufficient to confirm it. The resulting composite showed superior efficiency in the catalysis of nitrophenol compared to the bare MOF or single metal NP@MIL-101(Cr)-SO₃H composite, up to 90% of conversion or a third of the time.[138]

Moreover, Jiang et al. first presented Au/AgNP@ZIF-8 composites obtained by in situ galvanic replacement.[139] Initially, ZIF-8 was synthesized and impregnated by a Ag ion solution, chemically reducing the Ag by NaBH₄. The AgNP@ZIF-8 composite was immersed in a solution of gold and silver[140,141] and, through galvanic replacement, a layer of silver/gold was grown on the surface of the AgNPs. The composite retained ZIF-8's crystalline structure (XRD) after the galvanic replacement, confirming the presence of Ag and Au by EDS. Although the particles are homogeneously distributed in the MOF whether the NP were in the pores or in the matrix was not investigated.

2.4.2 Hollow structures

In recent years, a strategy has been explored in order to maximize the surface of nanomaterials: the synthesis of hollow structures.[142,143] As a general concept, a sacrificial template is here employed, the material growing on this support which shapes the NP. After growth, the template is then removed and the obtained material constitutes a stable hollow structure, similar to a capsule. Only few examples of this strategy can be found in the literature so far because it entails fine tuning of the synthetic conditions.[144,145] Indeed, the destruction method used to decompose the mold should not degrade the MOF, and the hollow structure should retain the morphology even without its mold.

This approach was initially employed for applications in catalysis but it is starting to find its purpose in the detection of biological compounds. In that matter, HKUST-1 has broadly been used as MOF.[146] Using octahedral Cu₂O NPs as source of copper for the MOF, in presence of trimesic acid, HKUST-1 is formed through oxidative dissolution, leading to yolk-shell Cu₂O@HKUST-1 composite (~350nm). This composite was used to in situ reduce gold through chemical reduction between the gold ions and the remaining oxide particle. The final composite presented a hollow structure with several AuNPs with sizes from 5 to 50 nm located on the inner wall MOF nanocage.

In an attempt to obtain a similar nanocomposite (~300nm with an internal cavity of ~150nm), the copper oxide particles were first used to reduce gold salt to AuNP on the surface through the same redox reaction.[147] The material was then suspended in dimethylacetamide (DMA) in the presence of the trimesic acid ligand. Here again, HKUST-1 is crystallized via a coordination replication reaction, using the copper from the oxide particle. The composite showed a homogenous distribution of the NPs seemingly inside of the MOF nanocage and high thermal stability (200°C). This material has been tested for the oxidation of carbon monoxide and the detection of glutathione.[147,148]

Moreover, hollow structures have also been obtained based on ZIF-8 using polystyrene nanospheres as sacrificial template.[149] These are terminated by carboxylic acid, which acted as an anchor for the ZIF-8 crystallization via solvothermal reaction in methanol. The nanomaterial was then impregnated by gold or silver ions. The material underwent a temperature treatment at 700 °C under inert atmosphere, where the polystyrene was pyrolyzed and the metal was reduced. The resulting composites was ~97 nm-thick (which represents ~72% of the initial thickness) homogeneous ZIF-8 hollow balls with numerous metal NP of 4.5 ± 0.9 nm in the case of gold and 9.6 ± 8.3 nm in that of silver, as evidenced by HRTEM, DRX and EDS. The location of the NP is not confirmed but they are homogeneously dispersed in the MOF thickness

2.4.3 Layered materials

A layered material refers here to a sandwich like structure, where compartmentalized layers of different materials can be distinguished. On this subject, a recent study of PtNP@UiO-66-NH₂ (~156.1nm, and a polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.177) was reported by Liu et al.[150] On a PVP-coated PtNP core of 3-4 nm, UiO-66-NH₂ was successfully grown using solvothermal synthesis in mixed solvents, dimethylformamide and acetic acid. After washing, the material was dispersed in an aqueous AuNP growth solution and PVP. The mixture was stirred for a few minutes and it turned dark blue, indicating the presence of a AuNP layer on the outer surface of the MOF. The presence of platinum and gold was confirmed by EDS. The gold shell is interesting because it is the only inorganic material approved for photothermal laser ablation. In fact, the material showed high thermal conversion upon irradiation (increasing up to 30°C in 5 min). Also, Liu et al. reported a conceptually similar strategy, combining MOFs, plasmonic NPs and magnetic NPs (MNP), with MIL-100(Fe). This porous material is composed by trimesic acid and iron forming [Fe₃(μ₃-O)(COO)₆] SBUs which are connected by trimesic acid to form super tetrahedron with mtn topology . [151] In this approach, the iron oxide MNP constitutes the core, on which MIL-100(Fe) was deposited layer by layer through solvothermal synthesis. Then, MNP@MIL-100(Fe) nanocomposite (~450nm) was stirred in a PtNP solution, resulting in the formation of a layer of PtNP on the MOF outer surface. The MOF and PtNP layering were subsequently repeated until reaching the desired size. The sandwich-like layering was evidenced by TEM and EDS, confirming the successful compartmentalization of the materials; layers of Pt and Fe can be observed by EDS mapping.

2.4.4 Combined approaches

Different strategies can be applied on one material, namely using a core-shell NP@MOF composite for NP encapsulation, to maximize the photo-property. Recently, Han et al. reported a AuNP@PdNP@PtNP@MOF-74(Zn) nanocomposite.[134] Au/Pd NPs of 14 nm were used as the core for the growth of Au/PdNP@MOF-74(Zn) bi-metal-core shell composite. This material was then actively stirred as a PtNP (2.7 nm) colloidal solution was added dropwise, to allow the NPs to penetrate the pores, leading thus to the encapsulation of the NPs into the pores of the core-shell composite. The final nanocomposite (523±37nm) showed a homogeneous distribution of PtNPs, as evidenced by EDS mapping and a porosity decrease, suggesting that the particles are indeed inside of the MOFs porosity.

This methodology of combining two approaches has also been reported using UiO-66. Likewise, the core-shell composite Au@Pd@UiO-66 (405±23nm) was first synthesized and then, resuspended under vigorous magnetic stirring while PtNP were introduced one drop at a time.[93] XRD analysis showed the presence of crystalline gold, palladium and platinum through

characteristic peaks. Interestingly, the homogeneous dispersion of the metal NPs was confirmed by EDS mapping, although whether the NP are inside the porosity or in the matrix has not been confirmed.

In a different strategy, up-conversion NPs $\beta\text{-NaYF}_4\text{:Er,Yb}@ \beta\text{-NaYF}_4$ were applied to synthesize composites from UiO-66-NH₂, this material was then used in situ for the chemical reduction of gold.[152] The composite was suspended in oleylamine and heated under inert atmosphere before the gold salt was introduced. Note here that the oleylamine served as the solvent, as well as the reducing and the stabilizing agent. The final nanocomposite (~300nm) was evaluated as a physiological thermometer.

3. Applications

As described in the introduction, plasmonic NPs have proven their relevance in the field of bioapplications, particularly as biosensors and nanoheaters. MOFs, on the other hand, have particularly been of use in biomedicine as drug carriers, taking full advantage of their high porosity. This section will present the most recent advances in plasmonic@MOF nanocomposites, particularly in therapy and biosensing, by advantageously combining the photo-activity of plasmonic NPs and the MOF's porosity.

3.1 Therapy

Many efficient drugs are associated to considerable side-effects, sometimes even toxicity.[153–155] This can be overcome by employing nanocarriers as drug delivery systems (DDSs). When combining the highly porous and versatile structure of biocompatible nanoscaled MOFs (nanoMOFs), associated with exceptional drug payloads and controlled release, with plasmonic NPs, it is possible to obtain smart DDSs. A key point is to deliver the active cargo specifically at the targeted site. For instance, upon their intravenous administration, the nanocarriers will be biodistributed to different organs in the body. However, the release of the active ingredients will only be released upon the application of a specific stimulus, intrinsic or external ones.[156–158] Intrinsic stimuli come from the difference in biochemistry between healthy and unhealthy cells, which are often translated into changes in the cell environment (e.g. lower pH). This particularity could trigger the drug release (e.g. pH-responsive formulations).[159] In contrast, external stimuli such as light, heat or a magnetic field, are implemented from the outside. In the particular case of light, two phenomena have broadly been reported; photodynamic therapy (PDT) and photothermal therapy (PTT). The former refers to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by irradiation, whereas in photothermal therapy, the irradiation leads to an increase in temperature and cell ablation (see Figure 3).[160,161] In the case of plasmonic NP@MOF composite, the excitation of the plasmon band (laser irradiation at LSPR wavelength) leads to heating, promoting the release of the active cargo by thermo-enhanced diffusion. Furthermore, in order to avoid cell damage, materials with plasmon outside of the biological window are favored, i.e. near infrared (NIR).[162,163] Lastly, the size of the DDS is important particularly for intravenous administration (200nm or less), so they can be carried by the blood stream without creating blockages.

In this line, AuNP@ZIF-8 core-shell nanocomposites (~60.84 ± 10.42 nm core and 89.84 ± 15.45 nm shell) have been employed as nanocarriers for the fluorescent antitumoral drug doxorubicin (DOX) (47% loading and 90% entrapment).[164,165] He et al. showed that the obtained

composite exhibits pH and light responsive release as well as phototherapeutic properties, while demonstrating a good biocompatibility.[166] AuNP@ZIF-8 showed a 72% increase in apoptosis after 30 min of irradiation with a laser at 514 nm; AuNP@ZIF-8@DOX 25% in apoptosis before irradiation and 98% after irradiation, in the exposed cells. These results indicated that the phototherapeutic effect of the nanocarrier was combined with the one of the doxorubicin. A more recent example was published by Carrillo-Carrión et al. using AuNS@ZIF-8 nanocomposites, where the use of near infrared (NIR) light led to the excitation of the core AuNS plasmon.[60] The heat generated by the composite led to a temperature gradient which enabled the triggered release of the cargo, proving the NIR triggered release of the cargo. Furthermore, the composite was functionalized with poly(methyl acrylate) (PMA), an amphiphilic polymer, to enhance the colloidal stability in aqueous media, including biological conditions. The PMA-coated nanocomposite showed great colloidal stability (no change in dynamic light scattering (DLS)) even after 7 days. Cell viability on HeLa cells (cervical cancer cell line) and A549 cells (adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cell line) evidenced the biocompatibility of the composite. Finally, the in vitro study showed that without irradiation, the cargo stayed within the porosity of the nanocarrier, whereas when irradiated the cargo was progressively released (up to 35%) over 24 hours.

In recent years, porphyrin based nanoMOFs have attracted a growing interest in therapy, due not only to their high porosity for drug payload, but also their potential in PDT. [153,154] Indeed, porphyrins' high extinction coefficient in the red-light region and high singlet oxygen quantum yield can, upon irradiation, induce the formation of ROS which are detrimental to cancer cells.[169] Recently, Zhou et al. reported core-shell AuNR@PCN-222, with good biocompatibility (as proven by cholecystokinin (CCK-8) assay), for combined therapy, taking advantage of the photodynamic (PCN-222) and photothermal properties of the AuNRs.[170] Specifically, light emitting diode (LED) (640 nm, 20 mW cm⁻²) irradiation generated singlet oxygen (PDT), and 808 nm laser irradiation increased the temperature (PTT), thus combining PDT and PTT. The anti-tumor activity of the composite was tested in vivo against a 4T1 breast tumor-bearing mice model. The study showed that irradiation at 808 nm led to a localized and controlled increase of the temperature in mice, proving its phototherapeutic effect. When irradiating at 640 nm, the photodynamic properties prevailed. Eventually, when combining the two approaches, the tumor drastically decreased in volume and size, demonstrating the in vivo efficacy of the formulation. Moreover, another porphyrin-based MOF, PCN-224(Zr), has been proposed for therapy. In this instance, PtNPs were reduced inside PCN-224 (location in porosity or framework was not determined)[171] The resulting nanocomposite (~150nm) was employed for sonodynamic therapy. This approach was favored over photodynamic because of cost efficiency and portable use (in real life applications), as well as deep penetration. Similarly, to photodynamic therapy, sonodynamic therapy requires oxygen in order to produce ROS.[172] In this sense, PtNPs can convert the over-expressed H₂O₂ at tumor sites to relieve hypoxia, thus optimizing the sonodynamic therapy. Cellular acoustic toxicity study was performed on BxPC-3 cells at different acoustic power, showing toxicity from 0.3 W·cm⁻² and plateauing from 0.7 W·cm⁻². Furthermore, the composite was also used as nanocarrier for glucose oxidase (35% loading efficiency), to reduce the glucose in tumorous cells, causing the cells to starve. The effect on the size of tumors was investigated in mice. Results showed the high efficacy of the combined strategy by means of the reduction of the tumor's volume: glucose oxidase and sonotreatment 90% (after 15 days),

the composite with glucose oxidase 30% and the composite without glucose oxidase but with sonotreatment 37%. Thus, a synergistic effect of the starvation and sonodynamic treatment was nicely proven.[171]

Another nanocomposite carrier was developed employing MIL-101(Fe)-NH₂. [173] On this regard, AuNR@MIL-101(Fe)-NH₂ was synthesized, functionalizing its outer surface with carboxylatopillar[5]arenes, a supramolecular nanovalve acting as a stimuli sensitive gate (Figure 4a). The MOF was selected for its high drug payload, and superior biocompatibility. The nanocomposite (215±6 nm) was then loaded with the anti-cancer drug 5-fluoracil (5-FU; 400mg/g loading). [174] The porous material was combined with AuNRs to impart photothermal properties, whereas the nanovalves add pH/calcium-triggered release of the payload in response to the changes of external environments. The studies showed that lower pH (4-5) favored the release of the 5-FU cargo, as well as an increase in cargo release at higher concentrations of calcium. Indeed, at pH=5 and a concentration 5 mM of Ca²⁺ under periodic 808 nm irradiation, the nanocarrier released about 50% of the total 5-FU. The in vivo study showed specific located thermal response with thermographic images. As well as a clear relative tumor volume decrease, 60 % for 5-FU alone, 75% for the irradiated composite without 5-FU and the 5-FU loaded composite without irradiation, and finally, nearly 100% for the irradiated 5-FU loaded nanocomposite. Thus, proving the associational effect of the drug and the PTT.

Another example of MIL-101(Fe)-NH₂ composite for PTT was investigated by Zhang et al. [175] In this research, AuNS@MIL-101(Fe)-NH₂ was functionalized to specifically target triple-negative breast cancer cells (TNBC) (Figure 4b). The aforementioned core-shell nanocomposite (200nm) was coated with PEG-NH₂ to increase its colloidal stability. In addition, the targeted peptide ZD2, which can specifically target extradomain-B fibronectin and overexpressed in TNBC cells, was covalently conjugated in the amino groups of the PEG-NH₂. The AuNSs serve for PTT and the iron MOF for MRI, which in combination with the conjugated peptide for cell selectivity, made this nanocomposite a promising theranostic agent. [176,177] The nanocomposite possessed excellent performances both T1-weighted magnetic resonance (MR) and PTT. Furthermore, their good biocompatibility was proved in vitro and in vivo. Finally, the targeted specificity of the peptide was demonstrated due to the high affinity to TNBC cells in comparison with other subtypes of breast cancer. Indeed, with the peptide functionalized nanocomposite the temperature increase was localized at the tumor site. Tumor volume decrease was monitored, resulting in 0% for the control and the peptide without irradiation, around 80% for the irradiated composite and nearly 100% for the peptide functionalized composite. Furthermore, the survival rate was evaluated, finding 100% for the mice injected with the functionalized composite, and around 0% for the mice injected with the non-functionalized composite, proving the necessity of the peptide targeted therapy and the PTT efficiency.

On the other hand, several amino functionalized MOF-based nanocomposites were investigated by Liu et al. for PTT. [150] MIL-88-NH₂ (~200nm), MIL-101-NH₂ (~500nm), Fe-IRMOF-3 (~1.5µm), UiO-66-NH₂ (~120nm), and Pt@UiO-66-NH₂ (~150nm) were covered by a shell of gold. Then, a highly potent photo-sensitizer against microbes and cancer cells, chlorin e6 (Ce6), was loaded (6%) into the composites. [178] The UiO-66-NH₂ nanocomposites with particles size suitable for intravenous administration, demonstrated low cytotoxicity in human breast cancer cells line (MCF-7) and the H₂O₂ degradation was evaluated using MAK164, an intracellular H₂O₂ assay.

Irradiation at 808 nm triggered the PTT due to the gold shell and at 670 nm the formation of ROS (Ce6). Different power densities and composite concentrations were tested for the PTT; optimal thermal response being at $60 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and $1\text{W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. At a concentration of $60 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ composite, the H_2O_2 degradation was nearly 100%. Finally, the in vitro tests showed that combined irradiation killed about 82% of cells when the first irradiation only 55% and the second 60%, proving the combined effect of PTT and PDT.

3.2 Biosensing

Biosensors constitute a chemical device which produce a detectable signal proportional to the targeted analyte (Figure 5). Different parameters are discussed in order to evaluate the efficiency of said sensor, including the limit of detection (LOD), which refers to the smallest amount an evaluate that the device can detect, and the linear range of detection, which means the range in which the signal is proportional to the targeted analyte.[179–181]

In this respect, PdNP@MIL101-NH₂ was used for cancer diagnostics,[117] specifically for the electrochemical detection of telomerase activity, as a biomarker for the early stage cancer detection (overexpressed in >85% tumors).[182] Electrochemical methods allowed a simple, low-cost, and sensitive detection of telomerase activity. In this line, PdNPs are promising material because of their proven electrocatalytic performance. The MIL-101-NH₂-based composite enhanced the composite's stability and its ability to bond to analytes through H bonds, whilst leaving the PdNPs highly accessible and active. Furthermore, this composite, grafted with capture DNA (cDNA) to favor binding to telomerase, was dip-coated on a gold electrode and used for differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). The telomerase activity was related to the amount of the adsorbed Pd@MIL101-NH₂-cDNA probe with wide dynamic range, 5×10^2 to 1.62×10^7 HeLa cells·mL⁻¹ and low limit of detection 11.25 HeLa cells·mL⁻¹.

Moreover, a bimetallic Ni/Cu-MOF composite in combination with carbon nanotubes and AuNPs and antibodies was used for the detection of tumor necrosis factor-alpha.[183] This factor is an inflammatory cytokine involved in many processes, and a level increase has proven cancer, arthritis, diabetes and Alzheimer.[184] Thus, Yola et al. investigated the detection of this factor by combining immunologic voltametric methods, evidencing an impressive LOD $2.0 \text{ fg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$.

Also, AuNPs@HKUST-1 nanocomposites were used for the electrochemical detection of glutathione via cuprous chloride output signal.[148] Glutathione (GSH) is a fundamental biomarker, involved in many biological processes, such as reducing free radicals which can attack DNA.[185] Au@HKUST-1 was put in contact with chlorine ions, leading to an enhancement of the solid-state electrochemistry of CuCl (Cu of MOF). However, in the presence of glutathione, the signal was dampened due to what is referred to as crowding effect. This effect is explained by the formation of the non-electroactive Cu-GSH compounds, and increased the sensitivity of the sensor. The material showed satisfactory results in several complex vegetal and serum samples and a LOD=2.5 pM.

Finally, microspheres ($\sim 2\mu\text{m}$ of the nickel benzene-tricarboxylate Ni-BTC ($S_{\text{BET}} \sim 830 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$) were decorated with AuNPs to form a glucose sensor.[186] MOFs tend to present low electron conductivity, hence the addition of highly conductive AuNPs. The combined effect of AuNPs and the Ni-MOF seemed to facilitate the fast charge transfer, demonstrating a high efficient glucose detection, with a wide detection range ($5\text{--}7400 \mu\text{M}$) and high sensitivity ($1447.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). Likewise, taking advantage of another Ni-MOF, Chen et al. presented a nanocomposite for the

electrochemical detection of glucose. Here, the Ni-MOF was decorated with AuNPs (~30nm), NiO and Ni NPs to form an electrode, which showed great particularly in terms of LOD (0.1 μ M), linear detection range and sensitivity (2133.5 mA $M^{-1}\cdot cm^{-2}$).[187]

4. Conclusion

Diverse approaches exist to synthesize NP@MOF composites, with proven good efficiency particularly in therapy and biosensing. Effectively, NP@MOF nanocomposites appear to enhance the properties of both, the MOF and plasmonic NP. Depending on the nature and mode of association, the properties of one or the other may be predominant, favoring different applications. On the one hand, core-shell composites have been used in therapy and as stimuli responsive DDSs (mainly triggered by light) because they exhibit LSPR whilst retaining the high surface area of the MOF. Recently, MOFs providing extra-features have been also proposed: i) fluorescence, allowing the in vitro tracking of the DDS, ii) phenomenal surface area, permitting the loading of large drugs and, iii) photodynamic properties, leading to the formation of ROS and even combinational PTT and PDT. On the other hand, composites obtained by encapsulation and in situ reduction, with lower porosity as consequence of the NP insertion in the pores, tend to be used as sensors, taking full advantage of the LSPR of the NPs high density in the material. This results in higher sensitive biosensors (lower LOD). Also remarkable is the stabilization effect of the MOF over the NPs, allowing cyclability and use under harder conditions.

In recent years, more complex architectures have been investigated. First, mixed NP composites, layered materials and hollow structures, initially proposed for catalysis, have emerged as promising materials in biorelated fields (e.g. diagnosis, water decontamination). Such materials are highly sensitive electro-chemistry-based sensors due to: i) the potential difference of the two different metals in the case of mixed metal NPs, ii) the shape and distance between plasmonic shells in the case of layered materials and, iii) the increased contact area in the case of hollow structures. It is however paramount to note that these composites are still in their infancy, requiring a further improvement to control the homogeneous NP distribution, shell thickness and overall particles size, among others. Lastly, in an effort to impart additional properties to the MOF composite, another material can be added, e.g. up-conversion NPs or magnetic NPs. In this approach, the goal is either to obtain a multifunctional material or to tackle the same problem via different paths (plasmonic + magnetic PTT + hypothermia for cancer). Despite their interest, composites combining these three different approaches are very scarce.

Expert opinion

Despite the significant advances in the preparation of plasmonic NP@MOF composites in the last years, the complexity and reproducibility (multibatch and large scale) of their synthesis are still points to be improved. Thus, the scarcity of plasmonic MOF composite in general can be explained by the methodical limitations of the synthesis. Indeed, it is difficult to systematically obtain homogeneous composites, even more so when targeting nanoscaled materials. As many factors in the synthesis are intertwined, determining which ones are predominant in a system is crucial. The preparation of a composite is often the result of arduous fumbling and innumerable unsuccessful attempts, lacking the reported works from enough details and discussion on the failed systems as well as on the synthesis optimization, which will be of prime relevance to elucidate which factors are determining. In this sense, among the large number of MOFs

available, only few structures (mainly ZIF-8 and UiO-66) have been reported as plasmonic NP@composites. This is mainly related with the MOF synthetic conditions, mostly not compatible with the plasmonic NP stability and/or synthesis (e.g. high temperature, organic solvents, acids), making necessary to optimize the synthesis case by case to avoid the NP degradation and to allow a suitable integration of both systems. Regarding the stability of the NP, surface functionalization could be considered as an optimal approach. Even more challenging is to finely control the formation of the plasmonic NP and/or MOF at the nanoscale with an appropriate size distribution. The control of the synthesis could be solved by directing the reduction of Ag or Au ions. In this sense using MOFs with relevant functional groups (e.g. -NH₂, -SH) could be a solution. Nevertheless, opting for softer MOF synthetic methods would be favorable, requiring to adapt previous protocols. Furthermore, in recent years, research in greener and softer synthesis of MOFs has been investigated and rather fruitful, which may open up the research of plasmonic MOF composite with a larger panel of highly porous and robust MOFs. These highly refined materials would offer high precision and generally higher stability with regard to the lone materials. As DDS they can bypass the toxic effect of drugs combined with phototherapy on one hand and on the other hand they can offer high specificity as sensors.

Another important challenge to be tackled concerns the in-depth characterization of the composites. In particular, to precisely observe and localize the NP in the composite, cutting edge advanced techniques are required, being nowadays restricted to few specialized groups able to deal with instable matrixes (MOFs; beam sensitive porous and hybrid nature) and tiny objects (clusters, NP). Currently, TEM based characterization is one of the most powerful tools to accurately describe nanomaterials. For instance, computed tomography can nearly ascertain if the NPs are located on the outer surface, in the inner porosity or within the framework. These last might be associated with the creation of an important number of defects, which could strongly influence not only the porosity but also the active sites of the final composite. These defects could be advantageously exploited in several fields (e.g. catalysis), although could be negative when considering the composite stability. In this sense, the field of TEM characterization is moving forward in different directions, in operando conditions for instance. We believe that advancement in TEM will help to shed some light on nanomaterials and plasmonic MOF nanocomposites, in general. From a characterization stand point, additional issues should be considered. For instance, EDS techniques allows to roughly localize and semi-quantitatively determine the presence of plasmonic NP within a MOF matrix. However, some EDS peaks are hard to attribute and/or quantify when close to similar energies. As a common example, silicon peak (frequently present, as coming from wafers) interferes with the gold, hindering its correct estimation. Further, accurate quantitative analyses should be done by using suitable techniques (e.g. Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy ICP-AES). In that regard, sample preparation, usually not detailed reported, is as important as the ICP determination, since its previous digestion, extraction and treatment of the matrix will determine the accuracy of the data.

Furthermore, recent relevant biocharacterization, including in vitro and in vivo investigations, has allowed to better understand these, up to now unknown systems, demonstrating a high biosafe character in general and opening many perspectives in the biomedical field. In particular, plasmonic MOF nanocomposites have proven to be efficient stimuli responsive DDSs, particularly light-triggered, which could be combined to the fluorescence tracking or photoproperties (PTT, PDT). Nevertheless, colloidal and chemical (degradation and/or NP leaching) stability of nanocomposites in biorelevant media is often an issue. No studies have been found explaining the process of leaching or the underlying causes. Surface functionalization could help

to overcome these drawbacks in order to both: i) improve their chemical and colloidal biostability, and ii) tune the in vivo fate of the nanocomposite, addressing the target site (improving efficacy and decreasing toxic side-effects).

Regarding biosensing, plasmonic composites appear to have particularly high sensitivity for different analytes with very low LOD. This can be a very powerful tool in diagnostics, because detection only requires small amounts of the analyte and biosensor. Particularly promising sensors and DDSs are the hollow structures. Indeed, this approach could allow in future the encapsulation of relevant large molecules (otherwise excluded by size) inside the mold. The challenge here is mainly associated to find a mold degradation process compatible with the guest. These hollow structures could then be used as stimuli responsive formulations. Although currently their synthesis is complex and hard, in the following years it is expected to better control the synthetic parameters for reaching tunable hollow structures (e.g. size, thickness, shape, nature), to use highly porous and robust MOFs, and to make easier the selective mold degradation, among others. Using non-traditional methods could be here a prospective tool (e.g. microwaves, sonochemistry, photo/electrochemistry).

Concerning mixed metal NPs, layered and composites with three materials, need to be better understood, since nowadays only scarce examples exist. Further, up to now, these complex systems have been mainly investigated in catalysis and sensing, with very limited examples in the bioapplication field. The rationale behind this is bioapplication needs from many specific and constraint requirements, including the stability in biological conditions, the biocompatibility of their composition (ligand, metal, solvent...), the limited information on the biocompatibility and biodistribution of the material and the interaction with living entities, among others. These studies can be rather time consuming and can explain why such materials still in their infancy, and considered exotic by the “biologist” community, have not yet been tested in the biomedical field. It is a matter of time until these materials can be applied, being necessary to bring together many disciplines (e.g. chemistry, engineering, physics, biology, pharmacy, medicine). Similarly, to the standard approaches (encapsulation, core-shell, in-situ), considered initially only as catalysts and sensors, one could expect that biorelated uses of the more complex structures will follow in a near future.

Last but not least, the cost efficient and reproducible scale-up, and manufacturing of such nanocomposite is also a must to be addressed for their real-life application. In this perspective, greener synthesis often use water as solvent, rather than organic ones, which generally make it easier and more cost efficient to scale up. This in turn leads to a more realistic industrial transfer and commercialization. From the large-scale production arises a potential societal issue; assuming an efficient and reproducible large-scale scale-up, the production would still be quite expensive, making the DDSs or sensors only available in very developed countries.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Schematic representation of MOF synthesis.

Figure 2. Synthetic approach scheme of 1. Core-shell composites, TEM image adapted from [31] with permission from Copyright © 2019, Wiley.; 2. Encapsulation composites, TEM image adapted from [32] with permission from Copyright © 2017, Wiley; and 3. In situ reduction composites, TEM image adapted from [33] with permission from Copyright © 2017 Elsevier Ltd.

Figure 3. Scheme of the cellular uptake of a NP@MOF composite followed by laser irradiation and PTT (photothermal therapy) /PDT (photodynamic therapy) and drug delivery.

b)

Figure 4. a) scheme of the light triggered release of 5-FU from AuNR@MIL -101-NH₂ in cells reproduced from [165] with permission from Copyright © 2017 Elsevier Ltd b) Scheme of MRI imaging and OTT using from AuNS@MIL -101-NH₂ in cells reproduced from [173] with permission from Copyright © 2022, Wiley.

Figure 4. a) scheme of the light triggered release of 5-FU from AuNR@MIL -101-NH₂ in cells reproduced from [165] with permission from Copyright © 2017 Elsevier Ltd b) Scheme of MRI imaging and OTT using from AuNS@MIL -101-NH₂ in cells reproduced from [173] with permission from Copyright © 2022, Wiley.